

Generation of rotary molecular motion by out-of-equilibrium jumping between states with different energy surfaces

Mike Gilson, UC San Diego, from tweet 12/14/2020

System jumps between energy surface 1 (e.g. substrate-bound) and surface 2 (e.g. apo) in coordinates (x_1, x_2) , with yin/yang shaped energy wells. On landing in a "tail", systems slides to energy well in "head", leading to rotation in (x_1, x_2) plane.

Non-equilibrium jumping between the surfaces is driven by conversion of unstable substrate to a product at low concentration that dissociates from this "enzyme", leaving it in the apo form. For example, surface 1 might be without substrate bound, surface 2 is with substrate bound, and the non-equilibrium jump back to surface 1 results from catalytic degradation of the substrate.

